

Emotional and Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment as Determinants of Cognitive Performance

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of the Requirements for the Degree
of Master of Arts in Education
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APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis entitled “**EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMIANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE**”, prepared and submitted by **SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education**, has been examined and is hereby recommended for approval and acceptance.

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the influence of emotional-social intelligence and a positive learning environment on the cognitive performance of students. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed. There were 300 Senior High School respondents in one of the public secondary schools in the Division of Davao del Norte who were chosen through simple random sampling. This study used three adopted questionnaires. Mean, Pearson r and regression analysis were used as statistical tools. Results show that the students' emotional-social intelligence and cognitive performance were very high while the positive learning environment was high. The results revealed a significant relationship between a positive learning environment and students' cognitive performance, while no significant relationship between emotional-social intelligence and students' cognitive performance. Further, a positive learning environment predicts the cognitive performance of students. With this current proposition, that positive learning environment is to be successful in stimulation of the cognitive performance of the students. Teachers are also able to create and develop cooperative, constructive, and mutually satisfying relationships.

Keywords:- Emotional-Social Intelligence, Positive Learning Environment, Cognitive Performance, Descriptive and Correlational Designs, Regression Analysis, Davao Del Norte, Philippines

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DEDICATION

This

Study is

Dedicated to my family...

To my husband, Glenn, who stood by me in

My lowest moments, always providing me with strength and

Inspirations: to all my fur babies, who brought happiness and sunshine to overcast gloomy days ...

Truly, the Lord God is great!

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *Rationale*

Learning, modeling behavior, and reaching personal goals depend on cognitive processes, which are complicated mental operations (Lemes et al., 2021). Cognitive capacity thus affects human behavior and decision-making (Zhang et al., 2018). Furthermore, interactions with positive environments and related stimuli have been found beneficial to cognitive performance, particularly on executive cognitive tasks such as memory, attention, and thinking (Stenfors et al., 2019). However, a lack of memory correlates with poor computational skills and academic achievement (Batool, 2019). On the other hand, teachers have had serious concerns about attention problems (Infantes-Paniagua et al., 2021). When students are the focus of attention, problem-solving ability is reduced, inhibition becomes difficult, distractions increase, mistakes happen, and irritability and stress susceptibility are all raised (van den Bogerd et al., 2020).

At Texas Tech University, college students exposed to negative environments such as stress and anxiety can impair their attentional control in the context of cognitive performance, according to Ning et al., 2018. Moreover, in Jajaram City, Iran, children with lower cognitive profile scores did worse in school. They discovered that learners with attention deficit disorders and issues with short-term memory did poorly in school (Nesayan et al., 2018).

The 2019 TIMSS revealed unsatisfactory results, where the Philippines fared worst among 58 countries. According to the poll, thirteen percent of Filipino students scored below the common criterion, 1 percent above it, and 5 percent below the intermediate (Mullis et al., 2020). This means that education in the Philippines, lags behind the rest of the world mainly in primary education (Allawan, 2021). It can be traced to a few elements that have something to do with the students' poor cognitive performance and have an impact on their academic success. These elements were based on the use of a variety of tools to gather data regarding the performance of the students; one of these tools is an assessment of the students' cognitive abilities, which places an emphasis on the three cognitive domains of memorization of facts, procedures, and concepts as well as problem-solving skills (TIMMS, 2019).

Most senior high school students show poor cognitive performance in one of the Division of Davao del Norte schools. In the recent proficiency level report for the school year 2021 - 2022, around 40% of students in senior high only achieved at least 75% proficiency level, according to the senior high school coordinator. It shows that most essential learning competencies still need to be mastered by students. According to the guidelines for applying the most important learning competencies (MELCs, 2021), these competencies are what students need to develop the cognitive capabilities necessary for lifelong learning.

With the worries and difficulties many students are experiencing, the researcher felt it was necessary to conduct this study. Further, some studies correlate emotional-social intelligence to students' cognitive performance (Ruiz-Ariza et al., 2018) and a positive learning environment to students' cognitive performance (Law et al., 2019). However, the researcher has not found any studies linking the three variables mentioned in this study. Furthermore, the researcher has not found studies on the variables, especially in national or local settings. Hence, there is an urgent need to study the connection between emotional-social intelligence, a positive learning environment, and students' cognitive performance.

➤ *Research Objective*

This study's major goal is to identify which aspect of emotional-social intelligence and a positive learning environment has the greatest bearing on students' cognitive performance. The study specifically intends to achieve the following goals:

- *To Describe the Level of Emotional-Social Intelligence of Students in Terms of:*
 - ✓ Self-Awareness;
 - ✓ Social-Awareness;
 - ✓ Self-Management;
 - ✓ Relationship Management; And
 - ✓ Responsible Decision-Making.
- *To Identify the Level of the Positive Learning Environment Employed by Teachers in Terms of:*
 - ✓ Caring;
 - ✓ Fairness and respect;
 - ✓ Interactions with students;
 - ✓ Classroom management; and
 - ✓ Discipline of students.

- *To Determine the Level of Cognitive Performance of Students in Terms of the Following:*
 - ✓ Memory;
 - ✓ Attention;
 - ✓ Flexibility;
 - ✓ Self-perception; and
 - ✓ Thinking.
 - ✓ Self-perception; and
 - ✓ Thinking.
- *To Assess the Significant Relationship between:*
 - ✓ Emotional-social Intelligence and cognitive performance of students; and
 - ✓ The positive learning environment and cognitive performance of students.
- *To determine the singular and combined influence of emotional-social Intelligence and a positive learning environment on the student's cognitive performance.*
- *Hypothesis*

The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

 - There is no significant relationship between emotional-social Intelligence and students' cognitive performance.
 - There is no significant relationship between a positive learning environment and students' cognitive performance.
 - There is no domain of emotional-social Intelligence and a positive learning environment that influences the students' cognitive performance.
- *Review of Related Literature*

To assess the study's significance, this part includes multiple viewpoints, arguments, ideas, findings, and synthesis from academic journals and publications.
- *Emotional and Social Intelligence*

Emotional-social intelligence is the skill that allows us to interact well with others while also controlling our emotions. These abilities are numerous and comprise, among other things, our interpersonal, coping, self-control, and self-awareness capabilities. It is commonly known that an individual's internal and exterior conduct is cared for and controlled by a combination of inborn psychological traits. Social or antisocial behavior is a result of a person's well-developed psychological basis. It is made clear in the emotional-social traits that have been identified and are thought to be the basis for one's success in life (Bhaskaran & Portia, 2019).

Emotional and Social Intelligence exercises have a positive impact on understanding others who are different from oneself in social settings, acting in a way that is appropriate for others and different situations, communicating with them effectively, actively resolving interpersonal relationship issues, and having an open and flexible attitude (Won et al, 2018). Additionally, an individual needs emotional and social intelligence to be able to govern oneself, build social skills over time, and solve difficulties (Ulvay & Ozkul, 2018). Furthermore, the ability of learners to connect favorably with others, participate in school and the community, and achieve in both school and life is consistently correlated with their emotional and social intelligence. Specific emotional and social skills, such as students' capacity to comprehend and control the emotions of others and successfully address social issues, are linked with a broad spectrum of competence (McKown et al., 2021).

Further, emotional and social Intelligence can be defined as the human ability to decode the world's happenings and respond to them likewise. The ability to understand, manage, and behave responsibly in interpersonal situations is referred to as social intelligence; it is equivalent to interpersonal Intelligence, which deals with knowledge of social situations and is more appropriately called social cognition. Emotional Intelligence is the capacity to recognize and control one's emotions and those of others. It is the ability to restrain emotions and channel them toward tasks like thinking and solving problems. The capacity to control one's emotions, and uplift or soothe another person, are examples of the capacity to manage emotions (Naik & Shukla, 2018).

People with high levels of emotional and social intelligence are able to effectively regulate their own emotions as well as those of others, motivate themselves, and identify their own and others' sentiments. Additionally, in attaining a balanced and successful life, emotional Intelligence has greater significance than intellectual Intelligence. The role of emotional and social Intelligence in different leadership and management styles has emerged. Successful leaders are those that exhibit collaborative behaviors rather than transactional ones (Suzzette & Harriott, 2019).

The first indicator of the emotional and social Intelligence of students is *self-awareness*. The degree to which people are aware of their internal states and social interactions is referred to as self-awareness (Lawrence & Weisfeld-Spolter, 2018). Furthermore, without self-awareness, people cannot comprehend other people's viewpoints, practice self-control, develop creative works, or feel pride and high self-esteem. In other words, students must take into account their own development, learning, and others' perceptions in order to advance and learn. (DeMink-Carthew et al., 2020).

According to Lu (2019), a necessary by-product of learning is self-awareness. A personal crisis, whether internal or external, can result in a perplexing conundrum frequently marked by contradicting sensations and emotions that prompt a critical assessment of the current frames of reference. Emotional well-being and self-esteem are also enhanced by a healthy sense of self-awareness. It teaches students about who they are, the reasons for their reactions, and how to become a better version of themselves. Students must be self-aware to succeed. Students who are self-aware have confidence in their capacity to succeed, which enables them to excel in everything they undertake (Khayankij, 2019).

Self-awareness results in an advanced cognitive self-examination process and an enhanced process of self-identity formation. As a result, self-awareness is not only a phenomenological term but also malleable to the point that society can use this corpus of knowledge to control conduct. The ability to become the subject of one's attention or turn one's attention inward toward oneself are both examples of self-awareness. One becomes self-aware When reflecting on the experience of detecting and interpreting inputs. Many intuitively understand this experience; standing before an audience causes self-awareness. Self-awareness, however, is a multifaceted phenomenon that spans various domains and corollaries (Ariel et al., 2018).

The second indicator of the emotional and social Intelligence of students is *self-management*. According to Yershova (2019), self-management is becoming a talent for the younger values more and more because it involves time management and self-development. A personal development strategy should be created and implemented after thorough analysis. The goal of self-management is to ensure that an individual's cognition and self-growth, effective monitoring of their activities and results, scientific focus of their work, and development preparedness for success. The implementation of self-management strategies is the technique or strategy that is most effective at changing behavior in efforts to increase student learning independence. Additionally, this method aims to assist students in self-directing, planning, managing, and controlling their activities, particularly learning, in order to make the most use of their time (Puspitasari et al., 2019).

Self-management is a technique people employ to change their behavior. Self-management, self-regulation, self-control, and self-determination are frequently used interchangeably (Hoff & Sawka-Miller, 2019). Since over 50 years ago, there has been interest in using self-management techniques to enhance instruction. But there haven't been any published comprehensive literature reviews, and high-quality empirical research is rare (Simonsen et al., 2018).

Furthermore, Sithole (2018) concludes that teaching self-management skills to students before they learn new content may enhance their learning. Traditional split-attention education, which is frequently found online and in textbooks, is suited to be replaced with self-management learning materials.

Social Awareness is one of the indicators of the emotional and social Intelligence of the students. Social awareness acknowledges and empathizes with individuals from various cultures and eras (CASEL, 2019). Furthermore, behavioral modification, and flexibility in response to particular conditions are all components of social awareness. Social awareness is crucial for recognizing other people's feelings in diverse circumstances, including sympathy and empathy. Understanding other people is crucial for surviving and adjusting to multicultural environments from infancy to maturity (Van Huynh, 2018).

The capacity to establish and maintain positive interpersonal interactions is known as social awareness. Petrides and Furnham (2019) assert that social ties and social impact are vital components of social awareness. Sociable people engage with others more successfully. They can talk quickly and clearly with people from various backgrounds and have good listening abilities. Additionally, they contend that those with social awareness can better relate to others, appreciate and accept others' emotions, see things from their perspective, and build deeper relationships with them.

A decline in social awareness is one of the inherent effects of the value shift. Recent events like the demise of the collaborating culture, a decline in social concern, a rise in individualism, or even criminal activity, are evidence of this. The importance of education as a tool for socializing ideals becomes evident in the face of such issues. Education's primary objective is to develop students' moral character. As a result, societal ideals might be internalized while studying. The formation of students with a high level of social awareness is anticipated (Syaputra et al., 2018).

The other indicator of a student's emotional and social Intelligence is *relationship management*. Utilizing one's own and others' emotions to establish and maintain strong connections, communicate effectively, and motivate and influence others is the practice of relationship management (Raghubir, 2018). Furthermore, relationship management also takes into account the vital dynamic of contact between students and teachers. Effective teaching and learning cooperation requires relationships (Rovida et al., 2020)

Moreover, to establish and preserve a positive relationship between students and academic institutions, relationship management employs a customer service strategy specific to each institution's viewpoint (Srisakonsub et al., 2019). Positive student experiences and school satisfaction are produced by using student relationship management. The provision of services for students is crucial and the fundamental duty of the school; as a result, all service regions should be covered, and adequate resources should be made available (Phuengrod et al., 2021).

The last indicator of a student's emotional and social Intelligence is *responsible decision-making*. Young teenagers are courageous, curious, and adventurous. At the heart of this transition to autonomy and independence are decisions over where to explore, what activities to engage in, and with whom to engage. These deliberate and impulsive decisions are essential to shaping teenagers' identities. Furthermore, Students also require self-control, self-insight, self-distance, the ability to actively model their behavior, the capacity to set goals, the capacity to think beyond oneself, and the capacity to discover meaning in their lives if they are to make responsible judgments (Hanna & Minton, 2021).

One of the fundamental cognitive processes underlying human behavior is decision-making. Based on a collection of alternatives and a set of desired actions, it indicates a decision. Decision-making is crucial to human potential and should be more concise, especially when choices significantly influence personnel (Blaskova et al., 2018). This calls for the use of suitable adjudicative concepts and procedures. This causes various criteria to be used in motivated decision-making.

According to Latip (2021a), Students who are capable of making ethically sound decisions must take societal norms, safety issues, and other factors into account. By detecting, delineating, and evaluating situations, it teaches students to make wise decisions. Furthermore, students who have strong social and emotional skills tend to exercise greater self-control and make ethical decisions. It gives students information on what deeper learning is and how it relates to a student's sense of responsibility (Wang et al., 2019). If students grasp the purpose of learning, which is their responsibility, they will feel more accountable for their academic performance. When a person can make the proper option that is not offensive and does not injure others, students can maintain their interest in studying something and, as a result, increase their academic accomplishment, which is the fruit of character responsibility. One will be more responsible in their decision-making the more they comprehend other people's circumstances (Latip, 2021b).

➤ *Positive Learning Environment*

Positive learning environments encourage the development of competencies, inspire people to participate in various activities, and recognize individuals for the virtues and attitudes they exhibit. Thus, the learning environment impacts one's ideas of oneself and competencies, attitudes, abilities, and values. To encourage students to engage in and take ownership of their learning, one of the teachers' tasks is now creating a positive learning environment. Teachers significantly influence students' learning and implement new learning strategies into practice (Anagün, 2018).

Moreover, academic performance and behavior increased when students felt their teachers cared about them, which positively impacted teachers' caring behaviors. In addition, kind teachers who were eager to build relationships with them affected students' decisions to engage and stay in school. Student's behavior in the classroom and their motivation to participate in the learning process are likely to be impacted by teachers who foster a sense of community, develop respectful connections with them, and acknowledge their value as individuals. Recognizing the many viewpoints of students encourages culturally sensitive compassion, which results in more beneficial experiences for all students (Abacioglu et al., 2020).

According to De Geest & Lee (2019), students think more critically, put in more effort, and enjoy themselves in a positive learning environment where they feel welcomed and supported. Teachers who try to create a positive learning environment are likelier to engage in and give learning the attention it needs, improving learning outcomes and increasing teachers' satisfaction with their chosen profession. It is necessary to set ground rules to make the classroom a productive learning environment, such as respecting one another, appreciating everyone's contributions, and ensuring the space is physically and emotionally secure. To create a setting that encourages learning so that children can grow up without being afraid or feeling bad about themselves, it is crucial that the teacher pays closer attention and shows empathy. Students will grow emotionally resilient and resourceful in a positive learning environment, which will help them overcome obstacles to learning.

Furthermore, a positive learning environment is created when students feel appreciated and accepted by their peers and teachers, and studies suggest that in such situations, students do better academically and have fewer behavioral issues. Additionally, these conditions prevent high school dropout rates. (Johnston et al., 2019).

Fairness and respect are indicators of a positive learning environment. These concern politeness, respect for another person or their opinions, and consideration of the rights and situations of others. Most adults are aware of fairness and respect, and teachers play an essential role in creating a respectful learning environment for students. This may be beneficial in some circumstances, but it is only occasionally essential because students may learn respect by watching how adults, including their teachers, act toward others. Therefore, Teachers need to be aware of their regular interactions with coworkers and students. To

sum it up, students can be taught proper respect by observing teachers model respectful behaviors towards others (Cheprasov, 2020).

Moreover, fairness is fair to peers when doing a task, being fair also means honoring authors' work by attributing it, upholding the university's norms for academic honesty, and being fair to graduates when their actions support the worth of their degree. Respect is following assignment instructions, participating in class and demonstrating an interest in learning new things, contributing ideas to the academic conversation while acknowledging that others may disagree with them, giving credit where credit is due, and making an effort to do one's best (Manly et al., 2018).

The other indicator of a positive learning environment is *interactions with students*. Regardless of age or grade, teachers' interactions with students are regarded as fundamental strategies to enhance learning and development in the classroom (Chan et al., 2023). It has been discovered that teacher effectiveness and students' abilities to build self-regulated learning skills depend on interactions between teachers and students (Harper, 2018). Further, to offer fresh insights on teaching and learning, the daily interactions that take place in the classroom lay the groundwork for teacher-student partnerships (Pennings et al., 2018).

According to Cheng & Tsai (2019), interactions between teachers and students may be related to academic success, motivation to study, and student engagement. The effectiveness of the interactions between a teacher and students in a classroom is essential for the growth and learning of students. In addition, a warm and good emotional climate, support for students' autonomy and opinions, and sensitivity to students' needs are all characteristics of supportive teacher-student interactions. Student's academic and emotional-social intelligence have both been connected to observations of encouraging teacher-student interactions (LoCasale-Crouch et al., 2018).

Furthermore, student relationships can promote academic persistence, motivation, enthusiasm in learning, and a sense of belonging. According to the students, most contacts were beneficial and influenced their interest in learning. Student involvement, motivation, learning, and teacher-student relationships have been related to a sense of belonging to the institutions. Regular interactions facilitate the involvement of students in their learning process. Meaningful interactions in which students feel respected and valued and perceive teachers' interest in their academic performance and personal development help to improve the integration of social and academic learning. It also help students feel like they "fit in" with the school environment, mainly when teachers use active and participatory teaching techniques that make students feel encouraged and included (Rivera Munoz et al., 2020).

Classroom management is one of the indicators of a positive learning environment. Classroom management is a planning technique that helps teachers apply and create behavioral classroom protocols, such as how students enter and leave the room, sit in their seats, turn in their homework, and use the restroom. Daily tasks like managing paperwork and organizing supplies highlight the distinction between well- and poorly-managed classrooms. It can be difficult to effectively control behavior by preventing disruptive activity. Teachers training in various management techniques can avoid controlling instead of punishing students (Al-Bermani, 2018).

Moreover, the process of managing a classroom involves a variety of tasks carried out by both teachers and pupils. The subjects must meet the student's requirements, skills, and previous teaching objectives. The proper type of management enables efficient goal-achieving, the logical use of time and resources, and activities that match the subjects being taught. Additionally, students are deeply engaged in their work and give it their all; they know what is expected of them and generally happy with it, and there is only a tiny amount of time is lost due to confusion are some of the advantages of teachers who effectively manage their teaching process and the classroom (Delceva–Dizdarevik, 2019).

The last indicator of a positive learning environment is *the discipline of students*. According to Astuti (2020), discipline is adhering to established rules, whether set in writing or not. It is a feeling of self-awareness and the determination of the person to follow any rules and regulations that may be relevant. Discipline can be developed in a person through habit. A disciplined student will be able to divide his time between carrying out all daily tasks according to all local laws and being able to adapt to his surroundings. The ability to maintain discipline will make it easier for students to study than the inability to maintain discipline. Since disciplined learners always devote most of their waking hours to studying or productive pursuits. A person's desire to study might rise due to non-intellectual and psychological circumstances.

Moreover, when teachers and kids get along well, they might encourage students to follow the rules at school. The way principals and teachers act will have an impact on how students are disciplined. Discipline and the skills that pupils gain in school are strongly related. Teachers are held accountable for upholding the rules by teaching discipline. A disciplined school environment and a staff that upholds the rules encourage pupils to do the same, which can benefit learning. Student learning also affects how well they learn and their commitment to academic discipline. Many pupils do acquire knowledge in a less exact manner (Sanjaya et al., 2020).

➤ *Cognitive Performance*

The method or manner by which a learner organizes and manages information in order to receive, transmit, and, ultimately, behave is referred to as cognitive performance. People do not approach scientific tasks identically in the cognitive style. The cognitive processes that students use to process information have an impact on their academic performance. Therefore, education strongly advises that cognitive preferences and students' academic success be taken into consideration while establishing and putting into practice curriculum and instructional performance (Babayemi, 2019).

Moreover, cognitive processes include remembering, analyzing, understanding, judgment, reasoning, thinking, and communicating to learn and use knowledge. Cognitive functions include those attention, perception, memory, language, and problem-solving skills (Fadillah et al., 2020). There is a connection between cognitive capacity and learning in educational contexts; in particular, cognitive ability aids in predicting educational success (Heckman et al., 2019).

The self-regulation of cognitive performance is one of the critical components of learning, and the student's ability to do so impacts their success in school. Studies on self-regulated learning have focused on the skills necessary for self-regulation in academic settings like schools. Effective self-regulated learners actively set goals, select suitable strategies, schedule their time, prioritize materials and information, organize, and change their methods as needed, assess their progress by receiving performance feedback, and make necessary adjustments for upcoming learning activities (Effeney et al., 2018).

Generally, views on working memory capacity explain how sources of overstimulation can hinder humans' ability to perform cognitive activities to their full potential. Due to issues with the cognitive load required by the work, pupils may need assistance in understanding what is being taught during teaching. Students may experience difficulties with increasing their cognitive burdens when they work on challenging learning assignments (Brown et al., 2019). According to Oredein and Babalola's (2020) research, teachers' recent poor cognitive performance is related to their ongoing desire to use their expertise.

The first indicator of cognitive performance is *memory*. According to Savage (2018), memory is a dynamic, arbitrary, and intelligent process that enables us to consider the past. Memory speaks to our capacity to store, encode, remember, and retrieve knowledge and previous experiences. Establishing the time component of our mental architecture is a cognitive activity. It also plays a significant role in life by accurately portraying the past and presenting the option to draw from both the past and the present. Furthermore, it aids in maintaining consistency between what was and what was intended to be.

Memory is essential for successful learning since learning is linked to acquiring information and subsequent retention. To succeed, learned material must be transformed into knowledge and that knowledge into abilities. Acquired information from learning processes is therefore stored or left behind. The greater the chance students will perform better in their learning, the more information they can memorize or keep after learning. Further, visual communication has great potential to be used in the classroom as a helpful teaching tool to improve student memory. As a result, it can produce an excellent learning performance. Visual communication helps students remember information better, leading to deeper learning (Vanichvasin, (2021).

One measure of cognitive performance is *attention*. A receptive and cognitive process called attention makes us aware of arousing stimuli as they reach consciousness. These processes include orientation to sensory inputs, identifying signals for focused processing, and maintaining an alert state. For example, a teacher increases students' motivation before the lesson proper. In that scenario, the main details of the lesson material will be paid attention to and easily remembered. At the same time, less focus will be placed on unimportant or peripheral matters. While under-aroused students' attention will wander and be readily distracted by competing stimuli, over-aroused students' attention is excessively focused, preventing the processing or retention of pertinent lecture material (Rosegard & Wilson, 2018).

The most important aspect affecting how information is processed in digital contexts is the restricted capacity for attention. The complexity of the human environment is beyond the capacity of their finite cognitive resources. Additionally, there are countless activities that students could do at any given time and in any setting. If they possess the capacity for attentional allocation, they can emphasize only some aspects of their surroundings while excluding others (Lodge & Harrison, 2019) s). Furthermore, the directed attention resources to rest and recuperate, according to the Attention Restoration Theory, nature can easily attract attention (van den Bogerd et al., 2020).

According to Okoye & Favour (2019), the value of attention in learning and memory retention has long been understood by educators. Human attention is a diverse, intricate concept with many parts. It can be broadly characterized as the capacity of the mind to choose among many behaviorally irrelevant stimuli, responses, memories, and thoughts. Students are typically expected to pay close attention to the ongoing lectures in the classroom. Observations showed that students don't pay attention to lectures; instead, they engage in unrelated actions like fiddling with their laptops or phones. Many of them can be seen sneaking out of lecture halls, dozing off, or looking away from the front of the class, among other unhealthy behaviors. They might be observed conversing on social networking platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp, sending texts or making phone calls, snapping photos, viewing movies or pictures, and taking pictures. This requires more focus and presents challenges for instructors to address.

The other indicator of cognitive performance is *flexibility*. Students can conveniently juggle several parts of their lives, such as employment, education, and leisure, by engaging in flexible learning. When properly supported, this has a beneficial effect on enrollment, retention, and advancement; it broadens involvement; and offers chances to learners of all ages, backgrounds, races, and nationalities. Flexible learning puts the needs of the student first and encourages independence and self-reliance in its graduates, preparing them to handle the challenges of modern life (Abisado et al., 2020).

Students gain from flexible learning in at least one of the following areas: timing, location, speed, learning style, subject matter, assessment, or learning path (Muller et al., 2018). According to the widely cited definition by Li and Wong (2018), at least one of the following learning dimensions, such as time, place, pace, learning style, material, assessment, or learning path, must be flexible. As a result, it is essential to consider how learners' failure in the classroom relates to focusing and keeping attention and their lack of intellectual ability or motivation (Cicekci & Sadik, 2019).

The fourth indicator of cognitive performance is *self-perception*. People identify their own learning requirements, goals, and resources through a process known as self-perception, either with or without the assistance of others (Siminica & Traistaru, 2018). Self-learning is valued as competence in both the academic and professional worlds. Self-learning is a strategy used by students in teacher education programs to try to ingest the systematized knowledge provided in those programs.

With high preparedness for self-learning, students are aware of their role in the learning process. Notably, research has found no gender-based disparities in students enrolled in teacher education's self-learning practices. In contrast, more female students than male students reported having a high level of strategy awareness, per Mohamoud-Mahfouz and Hassan-Ma'Ajini's (2018) findings.

The last indicator of cognitive performance is *thinking*. Students will be better prepared for the changing and uncertain adult world if their learning environment in the classroom emphasizes critical thinking. Human thought can be made to be more balanced and balanced through concerted intervention and evaluation. However, when we become aware of this issue, this roadblock to living a fulfilling life, we utilize our thinking to sharpen our thinking. We build on and develop our thinking by using our ability to think more deeply. Then, flawed thinking decreased (Hove, 2019).

The highest level of thinking proficiency at which students flourish is cognitive competence. There are more than two pieces of information that can be used to compare critical thinking and a student's capacity for thought. If there are differences and parallels, students will inquire or comment to get more information and an explanation. Critical thinking is the process by which a person makes an effort to intelligently respond to questions that cannot be answered quickly and for which there is a lack of all pertinent facts (Supriyatno et al., 2020).

The most significant way for educators who use a critical thinking approach to instruction to discipline their students is to have them constantly evaluate the soundness of their justifications and arguments. Students' success in the classroom, the workplace, and life will all be directly impacted by their ability to function in the twenty-first century. Teachers could accomplish these goals with inquiry-based curricula covering regional, state, and federal subject standards.

➤ *Correlation between Measure*

Students with high emotional-social Intelligence predict cognitive performance, and study shows they will work better in their groups. According to Alves et al. (2017), self-awareness, self-control, drive, empathy, and social skills are all components of emotional-social intelligence. Lemos et al. (2019) stated that emotional-social Intelligence played an essential role in students' cognitive performance.

The research conducted by Martins et al. (2016) on senior high school students showed that emotional-social Intelligence correlated with students' cognitive performance. The other researchers also reported that there was a correlation between emotional Intelligence and the learning results of senior high school students (Lee & Shute, 2016). Similarly, Alves et al. (2017) asserted that emotional-social Intelligence could be used to predict students' academic success.

Studies have shown that students' emotional and social Intelligence has a strong relationship with positive learning environments in the classroom that will develop students' cognitive performance. Students are emotionally and socially intelligent and possess self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management that may enable or even constitute their efficacy. It is practical in effective learning environments that are conducive to student success. In addition, emotionally and socially intelligent students can better influence others, articulate clear and compelling visions, display sensitivity to their classmates' needs, mediate between conflicting individual and group demands, and embrace cultural diversity to increase cohesiveness in the classroom (Galler, 2015).

Moreover, the emotional and social Intelligence of the students is related to creating a positive learning environment. It enables teachers to understand the motivation behind behaviors. When students struggled in class, a teacher modified the teaching strategies and material to fit their emotional and social requirements. With the teacher's help, students can continue and progress

with their learning. By understanding student emotions, teachers can more effectively address disruptive conduct. Teachers can examine the motivations behind the behaviors in addition to the actions. Students' emotional and social intelligence can affect their mental health as they develop mentally, physically, and emotionally. Teachers must be conscious of these needs to create a positive learning environment (Ozorio, 2019).

Further, students' emotional and social Intelligence of students influences the positive learning environment and students' cognitive performance. Hence, emotional and social Intelligence creates character. They help us understand our own and other people's emotions and relationships. Our capacity to experience either happy or negative emotions and control how they manifest themselves externally results from the intrapersonal component of emotional intelligence. The learning environment aims to promote the students' socio-emotional development successfully. Teachers can build a cooperative, constructive, and mutually rewarding connection. Therefore, for a teacher to succeed, it is also necessary to have vital social and emotional intelligence (Birknerova, 2019).

The above-related studies were used in the construction of this study. Building a good relationship, creating a positive learning environment, and helping the students to be emotionally and socially stable are crucial. Accordingly, students' emotional and social Intelligence promotes a positive learning environment in the classroom. It is better if the teacher involves the students, discusses their problems, and tries to solve them. The teacher must give students a feeling that they are respected, which will work as a tool for creating a positive learning environment. Emotional and Social Intelligence focuses on learners. It also has substantial implications for teachers regarding classroom management and the skills they promote to their learners and themselves as role models.

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

The study anchored on emotional-social Intelligence as a predictor of cognitive performance, and those students with high emotional-social Intelligence will work better in their groups. According to Alves et al. (2017), emotional-social Intelligence includes self-knowledge, self-control, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Lemos et al. (2019) supported that emotional-social Intelligence is essential to students' cognitive performance.

The other researchers also reported that there was a correlation between emotional-social Intelligence and the performance of senior high school students (Lee & Shute, 2016). The research conducted by Martins, Alves, and Almeida (2016) on senior high school students showed that emotional-social Intelligence correlated with students' cognitive performance. Similarly, Alves et al. (2017) asserted that emotional-social Intelligence could be used to predict students' academic success.

In parallel, the emotional and social Intelligence of the students is related to creating a positive learning environment. If students had difficulty in school, a teacher would take time to adapt the teaching methods to meet their emotional and social needs. With these, students can continue and progress with their learning. Teachers can examine the motivations behind the behaviors in addition to the actions. Students' emotional and Social Intelligence can affect their mental health as they develop mentally, physically, and emotionally. To create a positive learning environment, teachers must be conscious of these needs (Ozorio, 2019).

In consonance, students' emotional and social Intelligence influences the learning environment. They help us understand our own and other people's emotions and relationships. Our capacity to experience either happy or negative emotions and control how they manifest themselves externally results from the intrapersonal component of emotional intelligence. The learning environment aims to successfully promote the students' socio-emotional development. Teachers can build a cooperative, constructive, and mutually rewarding connection. Therefore, for a teacher to succeed, it is also necessary to have vital emotional and social intelligence (Birknerova, 2019).

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

Presented in Figure 1 is the relationship between emotional-social Intelligence and a positive learning environment and students' cognitive performance. The study's independent variables are emotional-social Intelligence (Zhou & Ee, 2012) and a positive learning environment (Barge, 2012). The first variable is emotional-social Intelligence with the following indicators: *self-awareness* refers to the ability of the students to perceive themselves as unique individuals; *self-management* refers to students' class preparedness, paying attention, following directions, allowing others to speak without interruption, and working independently with focus, *social awareness* is the term used to describe how students behave in class, which helps to create a learning environment, *relationship management* describes how students keep up a constant level of involvement with their teachers, parents, and classmates., and *responsible decision-making* refers to students who are capable of making moral decisions based on safety considerations, societal norms, and other factors when it comes to one's behavior and how they interact with others.

The other variable is a positive learning environment with the following indicators: *caring* refers to the teacher's concern for the student's emotional and physical well-being, *fairness and respect* refer to the teachers' equal treatment of the students, *and interactions with students* refer to the teachers' strategies to encourage students' cohesiveness and cooperation, *classroom management* refers to the teachers' effective

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework of the Study strategies in managing classroom physical factors to support students' learning activities.

Moreover, the discipline of students refers to teachers' reinforcement to encourage desirable student behavior.

The dependent variable is cognitive performance (Indumathi & Namakrishnan, 2017) with the following indicators, *memory* refers to a student's capacity to absorb knowledge, retain it, and then recall it later; *attention* refers to students' ability to actively determine when and how they will learn by adjusting their skills, *self-perception* refers to students' capacity to perform in school successfully and is frequently cited as a crucial element in learning. *Thinking* refers to students understanding a set of associations and concepts with a specific aim in mind, possibly leading to a conclusion that is grounded in fact.

➤ Significance of the Study

This study will focus on emotional-social Intelligence and a positive learning environment as determinants of the students' cognitive performance in the classroom. The result will provide helpful suggestions for establishing a positive learning environment, defining and outlining the components of the essential aspects for effective teaching and learning, and creating a conducive learning environment. Moreover, teachers need to understand students' cognitive performance and know how to react accordingly. It can reduce stress levels if teachers can better understand the reasons behind students' cognitive performance and adjust their teaching strategies.

From a global perspective, a positive learning environment has been connected to emotional-social Intelligence and the development of the student's cognitive performance. This environment places a strong priority on instruction with a clear commitment to learning. Even if technology and knowledge have advanced, it is still important for schools to maintain a

supportive environment for learning that is very different from the past. Previous educational systems focused on instruction rather than on the student's performance. This is not meant to suggest that the teacher lacks classroom management abilities. A successful teacher cares about helping students while continuously adhering to the student's success on a journey toward ongoing growth and progress.

Furthermore, the findings will benefit the DepEd Officials. This will be a basis for strengthening the curriculum and other programs that will address the emotional-social Intelligence and the positive learning environment that contributes to the development of the student's cognitive performance. It will also act as a foundation for figuring out how to better meet the demands of the teachers in providing students with high-quality instruction. Additionally, it will assist the Division of Davao del Norte in designing and implementing policies that would increase instructors' levels of readiness, resulting in an improvement in student cognitive performance. The School Administrators will also benefit from the study. This will serve as the foundation for any potential future modifications to management and school policies, especially in creating a positive learning environment, which will cater the needs of the students' mental health. The outcomes and conclusions of this study will serve as a foundation for strengthening the activities, programs, and events being carried out in schools to support students' emotional-social intelligence, assess the methods of learning modality as well as the students' self-directed learning abilities, and improve students' cognitive performance. Next, the teachers are the beneficiaries of the study, as it will give them the current information regarding students' emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment related to their cognitive performance. Teachers will reassess their methods for teaching using various learning modalities in light of this information to better meet the individual needs of the pupils. It also provides teachers with valuable information about the history of anxiety and depression that are more likely to engage in risky and maladaptive behaviors of students.

Further, the students will also benefit from the outcome of this study. Since students are the main focus of this, it will be advantageous to them. The outcomes and conclusions of this study may influence the decisions made by various institutions, which will directly impact students. Further, this may be another technique to measure their cognitive function and build their intervention. It will also act as a reminder to be emotionally and socially knowledgeable in order to prevent being intimidated or subjected to verbal abuse from others at school. Moreover, the study's findings will be helpful to parents as well since they will encourage them to become more involved in their students' education. It will give them information about their children's emotional-social intelligence, self-directed skills, and engagement in different learning modalities, affecting their cognitive performance. Lastly, future researchers for it might serve as a resource for upcoming researchers who are doing studies with a wider scope and various respondents as a part of the linked literature. The findings of this study may potentially be used to investigate additional variables that affect students' cognitive performance.

➤ *Definition of Terms*

This study used the following important terms that are conceptually and operationally defined to establish a common frame of reference.

- *Emotional-Social Intelligence.* As used in this study, it refers to self-awareness, social awareness, self-management, relationship management, and responsible decision-making of the students.
- *Positive Learning Environment.* As used in this study, it refers to caring, fairness and respect, interactions with students, classroom management, and discipline of students in the classroom.
- *Cognitive Performance of Students.* As used in this study, it refers to the student's memory, attention, flexibility, self-perception, and thinking.

CHAPTER TWO METHOD

The methods and procedures utilized to acquire the required data were covered in this chapter. This comprises the data collection process, the research instrument, the research location, the research subject covering the respondents, and the statistical analysis of the data collected that was used by the researcher in the study.

➤ *Research Design*

The research employed a quantitative non-experimental research design using a correlation technique. Non-experimental research has an independent and dependent variable; however, the dependent variable's impact on the independent variable is observed without changing the independent variable. Administering a survey to a sample of the total population is suitable to characterize the attitudes, beliefs, behaviors, or features that will be used to describe and assess the level of connection or link between two or more variables or sets of scores. However, because this study employed mathematical and statistical methods to quantify data and decide whether to accept or reject the hypothesis, it also used the quantitative research methodology to explain problems descriptively and numerically (Creswell, 2014).

A vital component of a research study is correlational research, which is concerned with identifying correlations between two or more variables in the same population or between the same variables in two individuals. All social science fields continue to be motivated to conduct scientific research better to understand the connections and interconnections between human occurrences. That motivation outweighs the most distinct model discrepancies among research methodologies (Curtis, Comiskey, & Dempsey, 2016).

➤ *Research Locale*

Presented in Figure 2 is the map of the Philippines highlighting Davao del Norte, where the study was conducted. The study was conducted in one of the secondary schools of Carmen, Davao del Norte. Carmen is one of the eight municipalities of Davao del Norte, Region XI, Philippines, in the Davao region in Mindanao (Figure 2). According to the 2016 National Competitiveness Council report, Carmen has been a first-class municipality since 2014. Further, the Philippine Statistics Authority reported that this municipality has a population of 74,679 people. It is about 38 kilometers (24 mi) from Davao City and about 17 kilometers (11 mi) from Tagum City. It is bounded by Tagum City in the East, Panabo City in the West, the Municipality of Braulio E. Dujali in the North, and the Davao Gulf in the South.

The study focused on one of the schools in Carmen. For years of teaching experience in the said school, the researcher observed that the students experienced peer intimidation or verbal abuse. Problematic student behaviors limit their learning capacity and emphasize the importance of emotional and social intelligence. The study was conducted during the school year 2021- 2022. Shown in Figure 2 is the map of the Philippines, highlighting the municipality of Carmen.

Fig 2 Map of the Philippines Highlighting the Province of Davao Del Norte

➤ *Population and Sample*

The study's respondents were 300 senior high school students from one of the secondary schools in Carmen for the school year 2021- 2022. The students rated their emotional-social intelligence and the level of their cognitive performance. Furthermore, respondents were asked to evaluate the positive learning environment employed by their teachers. The senior high school students were selected as the study's respondents because they had extensive experience in the setting and could provide justifications for their responses to the prepared questionnaire. Junior high school students were excluded from the study since they were beginners and had limited experience in the educational setting.

The researcher used Slovin's formula random sampling technique using simple percentages wherein 300 respondents were chosen from the total population of 1,000 junior and senior high school students from this school. Moreover, the researcher used a simple random lottery technique to address the bias and administrative issues. Before conducting the study, the researcher considered the said technique to avoid the researcher's biases and prejudices. Informed consent and assent were given to the respondents with permission to be the study participants. Participants were not provided with any survey forms without their consent and the consent of their parents. The 300 respondents answered the standardized questionnaire on emotional and social intelligence, positive learning environment, as well as determinants of cognitive performance. The researcher administered the validated questionnaires through Google form due to the strict health protocol of the division, and face-to-face interaction was discouraged. Participants who willingly agree to participate in a study may, at any point, opt out of some or all its components. The respondent must be asked if they want to continue participating in the study by the researcher. The researcher is not permitted to access the respondent's record or any other confidential records for the research if the respondent withdraws from all aspects of the study.

➤ *Research Instrument*

Three adapted survey questionnaires were tested to obtain data by answering the research questions. The three sets of questionnaires were (1) The emotional-social intelligence consists of a 25-item questionnaire from Zhou and Ee (2012). The questionnaire has five indicators: self-management; self-awareness; social awareness; responsible decision-making; and relationship management; (2) The positive learning environment consists of 26 items from Barge (2012). The questionnaire has five indicators: fairness and respect; caring; interactions with students; the discipline of students; and classroom management; (3) The cognitive performance questionnaire consists of 36 items used by Indumathi and Namakrishnan (2017) with five indicators: attention, memory, self-perception, flexibility, and thinking.

For content validity, the researcher conducted internal validation. It involved discussions with the study's research experts. The three-part questionnaire was submitted for validation and approval by the expert panel. It obtained an overall rating of 3.57, which was described as an excellent validity index. The questionnaires underwent pilot testing among grade 10 students not included in the study. The pilot testing result was computed using Cronbach Alpha for independent and dependent variables. The results of Cronbach Alpha for both independent and dependent variables were .964 for emotional and social intelligence, .919 for a positive learning environment, and .969 for cognitive performance. The findings revealed the validity of the questionnaire's items.

The questionnaire was carefully designed so that the responders could complete it quickly. As a result, the set of surveys had a Likert scale with a five-point response system (Likert, 1967). A Likert Scale was a scale of ratings that asked a person to rate how much they agreed or disagreed with a statement. The following were the scales: always, often, sometimes, seldom, and never. The dependent variable will use a scale, (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) Neither Agree nor Disagree, (2) Disagree, and (1) Strongly Disagree.

The following range of means with its corresponding descriptions is used to describe emotional-social intelligence.

➤ *Range of Mean Descriptive Level Interpretation*

- 4.20 – 5.00 Very High This means that emotional and social intelligence is always manifested.
- 3.40 – 4.19 High This means that emotional and social intelligence is oftentimes manifested.
- 2.60 – 3.39 Moderate This means that emotional and social intelligence is sometimes manifested.
- 1.80 – 2.59 Low This means that emotional and social intelligence is seldom manifested.
- – 1.79 Very Low This means that emotional and social intelligence is never manifested.

In assessing the positive learning environment, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions are used as follows:

➤ *Range of Mean Descriptive Level Interpretation*

- 4.20 – 5.00 Very High This means a positive learning environment is always observed.
- 3.40 – 4.19 High This means that a positive learning environment is observed oftentimes.
- 2.60 – 3.39 Moderate This means that a positive learning environment is observed sometimes.
- 1.80 – 2.59 Low This means a positive learning environment is rarely observed.
- – 1.79 Very Low This means a positive learning environment is not observed.

In determining the students' cognitive performance, the following range of mean with its corresponding descriptions is used.

➤ *Range of Mean Descriptive Level Interpretation*

- 4.20 – 5.00 Very High This means that the cognitive performance of the student is completely decided.
- 3.40 – 4.19 High This means that the cognitive performance of the student is decided.
- 2.60 – 3.39 Moderate This means that the cognitive performance of the student is either decided or undecided.
- 1.80 – 2.59 Low This means that the cognitive performance of the student is undecided
- – 1.79 Very Low This means that the cognitive performance of the student is completely undecided

➤ *Data Collection*

The conduct of this study started right after the approval from the Ethics Review Committee (UMERC). March 7, 2022, was the day of giving the assent forms to the respondents. After the retrieval of the assent forms, the questionnaires were administered on March 21-22, 2022.

The researcher requested authorization to carry out the study in order to gather relevant data. Request university of Mindanao-Professional Schools Dean wrote a letter of request to the superintendent of Davao del Norte's schools and the head of the school where the study was done, noting in the letter that the adviser had advised and properly attaching an endorsement letter.

Before administering the survey, the researcher requested the Office of the Registrar's list of students enrolled in the school year 2021-2022, which was then used to calculate the survey's sample size. The researcher distributed and discussed the informed consent form to the respondents after determining the total number of respondents using the random sample approach using simple percentages.

To achieve 100% retrieval, the researcher gave the questionnaires to the respondents. The study presented the researcher to the respondents and discussed the goal of the study while distributing the questionnaires. Then, the survey forms were given to the respondents by the researcher. The respondents were given clear instructions on how to complete the questionnaires.

The statistician received an email from the researcher with the tabulated survey answer data, which was subsequently sent to them for statistical analysis. Next, The researcher gathered the student comments for consolidation, and the proper statistical methods were used to total and tabulate the respondents' responses in a master data sheet. Based on the interpretations and results, the researcher ultimately came to a conclusion and gave recommendations.

➤ *Statistical Tools*

The study's hypothesis was tested using the following statistical methods, with a 0.05 significance level.

• *Mean.*

This was used to describe the level of emotional-social intelligence, positive learning environment, and students cognitive performance.

• *Pearson-r.*

This was utilized to assess the relationship between emotional-social intelligence and the cognitive performance of the students and the relationship between a positive learning environment and the students' cognitive performance.

• *Regression Analysis.*

This was used to determine the significant influence of emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment and the domain of emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment that influences the students' cognitive performance.

• *Ethical Considerations.*

This quantitative investigation was notably impacted by certain important ethical questions and concerns. The study's approach gave rise to a few problems and worries. The right to perform the study, secrecy, and anonymity are all ethical concerns with this research.

The first challenge was a request letter submitted to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent asking permission to conduct the study.

The following study protocol assessment criteria were also considered:

- *Voluntary Participation.* To preserve their privacy and information, the respondents' participation is voluntarily and anonymous. The decision of the respondents to engage in the data collection and their ideas and opinions were respected by the researcher. Their rights to add to the body of knowledge were therefore carefully considered and respected after the respondents had been informed of the study's goals and advantages. Senior high school students were chosen as the study's sample since they have had a lot of time in the environment and can thus defend their responses to the questionnaire that has been produced. Junior high school students are not included in the study, though, as they are beginners and have limited experience in a classroom setting.

- *Privacy and Confidentiality.* The researcher respects the rights and privacy of the respondents and ensures that it will adhere to and observe the Data Privacy Act that protects the data being gathered right from the start of the study. The researcher should focus on critical ethical questions such as confidentiality regarding respondents' opinions and integrity. The researcher pledged to keep the study's records private and promised that whatever the study's final findings, they would not be shared with the respondents or any other community members.
- *Informed Consent Process.* The study will undergo informed consent and assent process since it is considered an essential part of the research ethics. The researcher will give informed consent and assent to the participants with permission from their parents to allow their children to be the study participants. No survey questionnaires are given to the participants without their parent's approval. The respondents and the relevant school authorities have agreed to and consented to the survey's conduct.
- *Recruitment.* According to how the respondents are categorized in the population and sample, the respondents to this survey are seniors in high school. This paper clearly presents the methods used for data collecting, survey dissemination, and other procedures.
- *Risks.* The researcher will see to it that risk minimization will be considered in this study. The researcher will firmly adhere to the IATF guidelines against COVID-19 to ensure that the risks and measures in mitigating possible risks will be appropriately reviewed. The respondents will be protected from physical, psychological, or social economic harm during the study. Researchers shall pay special attention to vulnerable subjects to avoid breaches of ethical codes.
- *Benefits.* The result of this study will benefit the DepEd authorities, school heads, and Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers to employ a positive learning environment and emotional-social intelligence in helping the students to develop their cognitive performance in the classroom, also, to the students who are the immediate recipients and beneficiaries of whatever proposed suggestions because of the findings. The researcher will not give money or different grades to the participants during the conduct of the study.
- *Plagiarism.* The researcher will make sure that all readings used in this study are paraphrased to prevent plagiarism, that no one else's work is misrepresented, and that all authors of cited literature are accurately cited to ensure that the research is adequate. Grammarly and Turnitin programs were used to check this work for errors in grammar and plagiarism.
- *Fabrication.* The researcher observes that paraphrase was used to avoid plagiarism difficulties with the literature used in this study. By condensing the original content that highlights the essential point using the researcher's own words while providing credit to the original author, the researcher employed summarizing and paraphrasing techniques and placed quotation marks on the text. Additionally noted and included in the appendices were instances of the usage of Grammarly, Turnitin, or other plagiarism detection tools.
- *Falsification.* Falsification is when research findings are altered or left out to support statements, theories, other data, etc. Throughout the study, the researcher ensured no manipulation of research instruments, materials, or procedures. Falsification also includes altering visuals or verbalizations that misrepresent the information or require too much line-reading. To ensure the participants' welfare and safety, strict attention was paid to the accuracy of all results, the suitability of the research, and the avoidance of conflicts of interest.
- *Conflict of Interest.* The best effort has been made to present the situation, taking into account all results, the suitability of the research, and the avoidance of conflicts of interest. Personal, professional, political, academic, or financial interests are only a few examples of these conflicts. The researcher made sure that any financial interests were prohibited, including employment, research funding, lecture or travel fees, consulting fees, and employee benefits from the employer. The researcher must go above and above to prevent their conflicts of interest from affecting the research's technique and findings. If unsure, speak with an impartial researcher or the Ethics Committee.
- *Deceit.* This study will be conducted without a hidden purpose. The researcher will not use deception and will protect the respondents from harm. The study aims to determine what domains in the emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment influence the students' cognitive performance in the classroom.
- *Permission from Organization/Location.* A formal letter is written to the Division of Davao del Norte authorities because the research was done in a formal manner and with apparent respect to ethical standards. Only after receiving official approval may the research be carried out.
- *Technology Issues.* The researcher notes that one issue that needs to be considered is the lack of scientific integrity in learning environments where technology is used to its fullest extent. The researcher will ensure that illegal software downloading is not applied in constructing this research. The researcher uses technology appropriately to support the development of this research paper.
- *Authorship.* The researcher contributes significantly to this study's findings, analysis, and results. In particular, the research adviser shall be acknowledged as the study's co-author. Researchers should make sure that the research adviser who served as a co-author is fairly and properly acknowledged for their work, and that the acknowledgements accurately depict their contributions. Finally, the submitted manuscript is typically written, revised, and approved by the researcher in their capacity as an author.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS

The data obtained from the respondents on emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment as determinants of the students' cognitive performance are presented, analyzed, and interpreted in this section based on the problem stated. The order of the discussion on the mentioned topic is as follows: level of emotional-social intelligence; the level of the positive learning environment; the level of cognitive performance of the students; the correlation between measures and the singular and combined influence of emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment on the cognitive performance of the respondents.

➤ *Level of Emotional-Social Intelligence of Students*

Table 1 shows students' emotional-social intelligence levels in *self-management, self-awareness, social awareness, responsible decision-making, and relationship management*, which is the study's first objective. The overall mean score of students' emotional-social intelligence level is 4.30, with a computed standard deviation of 0.68, implying that the response is homogenous. The indicator with the highest mean is *responsible decision-making* (4.44), with a descriptive level of very high. It is then followed by *self-awareness* (4.36), also described as very high. Next is *relationship management* (4.28), defined as very high again. *Social awareness*, with a mean of (4.25) is described as very high again. Finally, *self-management* has the lowest mean of (4.19), which is described as high.

The result implies that it is evident that students were aware of themselves and the people around them. Further, it is evident that students are accountable for their decisions and behaviors and that they are able to form relationships with others. The very high levels of responsible decision-making, self-awareness, relationship management, and social.

Table 1 Level of Emotional-Social Intelligence

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-Awareness	0.70	4.36	Very High
Social Awareness	0.65	4.25	Very High
Self-Management	0.71	4.19	High
Relationship Management	0.66	4.28	Very High
Responsible Decision-making	0.67	4.44	Very High
Overall	0.68	4.30	Very High

Awareness indicated that the emotional-social intelligence of students was always manifested, and the high level of self-management indicated that the emotional-social intelligence of students was oftentimes manifested.

➤ *Level of Positive Learning Environment*

Table 2 shows the level of the positive learning environment of students in terms of *fairness and respect, interactions with students, caring, discipline of students, and classroom management*.

As shown, the indicator with the highest mean score is *the discipline of students* (4.31) or very high. It is followed by *interactions of students* with a mean of (4.18) or high and followed by *caring* with a mean of (4.08) or high. *Classroom management* with a mean of (4.06) or high. Finally, the indicator with the lowest mean score is *fairness and respect*, with a mean of (3.94) or high. The overall mean score of the level of positive learning environment is 4.11, or described as high. This denotes that the respondents oftentimes observed a positive learning environment. Moreover, it has an SD of 0.73 ($SD < 1.00$), indicating the homogeneity of the responses for this variable.

This implies that the positive learning environment experienced by students in the school is evident. In addition, to promote student involvement and reduce disruption, teachers must be fair and respectful to the kids, care about them, and employ effective questioning, seamless transitions, and challenging yet engaging activities. Further, the school encourages the students' cohesiveness and cooperation and values their ideas and input. Finally, teachers and students work hand in hand to make the learning environment positive and conducive to all.

Table 2 Level of Positive Learning Environment

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Caring	0.69	4.08	High
Fairness and Respect	0.76	3.94	High
Interactions of Students	0.77	4.18	High
Classroom Management	0.73	4.06	High
Discipline of Students	0.56	4.31	Very High
Overall	0.73	4.11	High

➤ *Level of Cognitive Performance of Students*

Presented in Table 3 are the results of the cognitive performance of the respondents. Computations revealed an overall mean score of 4.33, or very high. The score was derived from the mean scores of 4.42 for *flexibility*, 4.37 for *thinking*, 4.36 for *self-perception*, 4.30 for *memory*, and 4.23 for *attention*. All the indicators are very high level.

Students' very high level of cognitive performance indicated that the conception was observed most of the time. The result is indicative that students were adaptable and had more perceptual ability. Further, improving cognitive abilities such as attention, memory, and thinking helps students to perform better cognitively.

Table 3 Level of Cognitive Performance of Students

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Memory	0.69	4.30	Very High
Attention	0.71	4.23	Very High
Flexibility	0.67	4.42	Very High
Self-perception	0.68	4.36	Very High
Thinking	0.67	4.37	Very High
Overall	0.69	4.33	Very High

➤ *Significance of the Relationship between Emotional-Social Intelligence and Cognitive Performance*

Presented in Table 4 are the results derived from the relationship between emotional-social intelligence and students' cognitive performance. The r-value of .009 or $p > 0.05$ or not significant for the correlation between self-awareness and overall cognitive performance, with an r-value of -.015 or $p > 0.05$ not significant for the correlation between social awareness and overall cognitive performance, r-value of -.014 or $p > 0.05$ and not significant for the correlation between self-management and overall cognitive performance, r-value of -.035 or $p > 0.05$ and not significant for the correlation between relationship management and overall cognitive performance and r-value of -.008 or $p > 0.05$ and not significant for the correlation between responsible decision-making and overall cognitive performance of students.

Table 4 Significance of the Relationship between Emotional and Social Intelligence and Cognitive Performance of Students

Emotional and Social intelligence	Cognitive performance					Overall
	Memory	Attention	Flexibility	Self-perception	Thinking	
Self-awareness	0.027 (0.643)	0.034 (0.557)	-0.015 (0.792)	-0.017 (0.771)	-0.006 (0.918)	0.009 (0.875)
Social awareness	.014 (0.813)	.007 (0.904)	-.040 (0.494)	-.052 (0.371)	-.024 (0.680)	-.015 (0.800)
Self-management	-.003 (0.958)	.029 (0.614)	-.036 (0.532)	-.019 (0.745)	-.046 (0.423)	-.014 (0.803)
Relationship Management	-.042 (0.472)	.031 (0.597)	-.039 (0.506)	-.038 (0.509)	-.071 (0.217)	-.035 (0.543)
Responsible decision-Making	-0.009 (0.881)	0.008 (0.897)	-0.009 (0.881)	-0.008 (0.896)	-0.018 (0.761)	-0.008 (0.894)
Overall	-0.002 (0.973)	0.025 (0.664)	-0.031 (0.596)	-0.029 (0.616)	-0.037 (0.528)	-0.013 (0.818)

➤ *Significance of the Relationship between Positive Learning Environment and Cognitive Performance*

Presented in Table 5 are the results of the relationship between a positive learning environment and students' cognitive performance. The r-value of .260 or p is less than 0.05 or significant for the correlation of positive learning environment and overall cognitive performance of students, with an r-value of .304 or p is less than 0.05 significant for the correlation between caring and overall cognitive performance of students, r-value of .217 or p is less than 0.05 significant for the interactions with students and overall cognitive performance of students, r-value of .234 or p is less than 0.05 significant for classroom management and overall cognitive performance of students, r-value of .232 or p is less than 0.05 significant for the discipline of students and overall cognitive performance of students. However, an r-value of .092 or p is greater than 0.05 is not significant for fairness and respect and the overall cognitive performance of students.

Table 5 Significance of the Relationship between Positive Learning Environment and Cognitive Performance of Students

Positive learning environment	Cognitive performance					Overall
	Memory	Attention	Flexibility	Self-perception	Thinking	
Caring	.289** (0.000)	.276** (0.000)	.313** (0.000)	.275** (0.000)	.239** (0.000)	.304** (0.000)
Fairness and Respect	.091 (0.813)	.120* (0.904)	.110 (0.494)	.049 (0.371)	.040 (0.680)	.092 (0.800)
Interactions with Students	.215** (0.000)	.190** (0.001)	.218** (0.000)	.180** (0.002)	.178** (0.002)	.217** (0.000)
Classroom management	.241** (0.000)	.229** (0.000)	.216** (0.000)	.163** (0.005)	.194** (0.001)	.234** (0.000)
Discipline of Students	.193** (0.001)	.122* (0.035)	.275** (0.000)	.271** (0.000)	.235** (0.000)	.232** (0.000)
Overall	.254** (0.000)	.240** (0.000)	.268** (0.000)	.212** (0.000)	.207** (0.000)	.260** (0.000)

When the measures of a positive learning environment are correlated to each indicator of students' cognitive performance, four out of five sub-indicators are significant to each other. That means the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. This signifies that the null hypothesis is rejected.

➤ *Multiple Regression Analysis of the Emotional-Social Intelligence, Positive Learning Environment, and Cognitive Performance of Students*

Considering that some indicators of emotional-social intelligence and a positive learning environment showed a significant relationship with a p-value of .000 with .000, multiple regression was employed to confirm the result.

Shown in Table 6 is the multiple regression analysis of the influence of students' cognitive performance. The regression model with four predictors, such as positive learning environment and emotional-social intelligence, produced an R² = 51.657 and F = 10.853, which denotes that emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment significantly influence the cognitive performance of students. Emotional-social intelligence and a positive learning environment do influence the conceptions of the cognitive performance of students.

On the other hand, exploring the p-value of each predictor individually, emotional-social intelligence has a p-value of .750, and positive learning environment has a p-value of .000. Among the indicators' only positive learning environment is a predictor of the cognitive performance of students because the p-value is lesser than α .05. The p-value of .000 indicates a significant influence on cognitive performance of students. This implies that a positive learning environment influences their conceptions of the cognitive performance of students.

Table 6 Multiple Regression Analysis of the Emotional and Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment on Cognitive Performance of Students

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.261 ^a	.068	.062	.40260	.068	10.853	2	297	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Overall mean Positive Learning Environment, Overall Mean Emotional and Social Intelligence

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	3.518	2	1.759	10.853	.000 ^b
	Residual	48.139	297	.162		
	Total	51.657	299			

a. Dependent Variable: OVERALL MEAN COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Overall mean Positive Learning Environment, Overall Mean Emotional and Social Intelligence

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.032	.387		7.835	.000
	Overall Mean Emotional and Social Intelligence	-.307	.116	-.023	-.319	.075
	Overall mean Positive Learning Environment	-.353	.092	.275	3.821	.000
a. Dependent Variable: OVERALL MEAN COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE						

CHAPTER FOUR DISCUSSION

Presented in this chapter are the discussions of the data on emotional-social intelligence and its function on positive learning environment as determinants on cognitive performance of students: level of emotional-social intelligence; level of the positive learning environment; level of cognitive performance of students; the correlation between measures and multiple regression analysis of the emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment as determinants on cognitive performance of students.

➤ *Level of Emotional-Social Intelligence*

The respondents' emotional-social intelligence level, derived from the responses, is very high. Indicators with very high response levels include *responsible decision-making*, *self-awareness*, *relationship management*, and *social awareness*. All have very high levels, which implies that it is evident that students were conscious of their surroundings and of themselves. Further, it is evident that students take responsibility for their decisions and behaviors and are able to interact with others.

The results are consistent with research from a number of authors that shows emotional-social intelligence is the ability to manage our emotions and engage with others in a positive way. Moreover, emotional-social intelligence includes the ability to manage one's feelings, control them, and use them for activities like problem-solving and thinking. Recognizing oneself, developing empathy, making ethical and moral decisions, nurturing positive relationships while avoiding negative ones (Naik & Shukla, 2018; Ulvay & Ozkul, 2018; Bhaskaran & Portia, 2019). As stated by (McKown et al., 2021), emotional and social intelligence encompasses skills, attitudes, and dispositions constantly associated with students' ability to positively interact with others, participate productively in community and school, and achieve success in life and education. This agrees with the result in which all indicators got a descriptive equivalent of very high.

Additionally, various intelligences are linked to particular emotional and social abilities, such as a learner's capacity to comprehend others' emotions, control them, and successfully resolve social difficulties. Emotionally and socially capable students are more likely to take part in academic activities, benefit from instructor interactions, collaborate with peers, imitate peers' learning practices, and give learning their undivided attention for long periods of time (Luo et al., 2020).

On the other hand, emotional-social intelligence is positively associated with students' cognitive performance. It is stated that students are said to function well in school due to their emotional and social intelligence in addition to their cognitive and academic skills (Taylor & Spinrad, 2018). It means that students are better prepared to succeed in school if they have self-awareness and social awareness, self-management skills, the ability to develop relationships with others, and decision-making skills. This is affirmed by the study of Waddy (2019), that even relationship quality in young students affects their academic progress because emotional-social intelligence is influenced by it.

➤ *Level of Positive Learning Environment*

The following variable considered in the study is the positive learning environment which is described as high. This is indicative that *caring*, *fairness and respect*, *interactions with students*, *classroom management*, and *discipline of students* are manifested most of the time in the classroom.

A positive learning environment is vital in reducing behavior issues to a minimum and encourages students to think and behave positively. Thus, one of the teachers' tasks is creating a positive learning environment. Teachers encourage students to engage in and take ownership of their learning, inspire them to participate in various activities and recognize them for their virtues and attitudes. Further, a positive learning environment impacts one's ideas of oneself, as well as their competencies, attitudes, abilities, and values (Anagün, 2018).

The study by Hannah (2018) supported the notion that a teacher must comprehend this cause and effect to organize their classroom to improve learning. Thus, the teacher's attitude affects students in the class. There will be a direct impact on the students within the classroom if a teacher lacks motivation or pessimism.

The study of De Geest & Lee (2019) emphasizes the strong relationship between students and teachers and promotes a safe and peaceful environment where teaching and learning are an essential focus. A positive learning environment is when the students think more critically, put in more effort, and enjoy themselves, where they feel welcomed and supported. Accordingly, teachers who try to create a positive learning environment are likelier to engage in and give learning the attention it needs, improving learning outcomes and increasing teachers' satisfaction with their chosen profession. Furthermore, a positive learning environment is created when students feel appreciated and accepted by their peers and teachers, and studies suggest that in such situations, students do better academically and have fewer behavioral issues (Johnston et al., 2019). This emphasizes that creating a positive learning environment can stimulate student learning.

➤ *Level of Cognitive Performance of Students*

The other variable considered in the study is students' cognitive performance, which is very high. The result is indicative that students were adaptable and had improved perception. Additionally, improving cognitive skills like memory, thinking, and attention helps children perform better cognitively.

Different studies supported these results. Babayemi (2019) demonstrates that a Different cognitive processing techniques affect students' academic progress. Brown et al. (2019) highlighted that instead of a lack of cognitive aptitude, students who participate in their classes also have trouble grasping the concepts being taught due to issues with the cognitive load required of the activity.

Babayemi (2019) explained that when a student performs cognitively on learning tasks, they are in charge of how they organize and govern their information, receive and transmit information, and, ultimately, behave. Further, when creating and executing curriculum and instructional performance, cognitive types and students' academic progress should be taken into consideration as crucial criteria. Finally, learning and cognitive capacity are related in educational environments. Cognitive capacity aids in predicting educational success. (Heckman et al., 2019).

Differentiation in terms of community, especially with schools, only sometimes ensures information security in the involved teaching and learning activities. Unfortunately, a few years of schooling can explain why education has no effect on IQ. As a result, instead of a lack of cognitive ability, students may find it challenging to comprehend the concepts being taught during instruction due to problems with the cognitive load demanded of the task (Brown et al., 2019). According to Oredein and Babalola's (2020) research, students' low cognitive performance in recent years is linked to teachers who still need to apply their knowledge.

➤ *Multiple Regression Analysis of the Emotional-Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment As Determinants of Cognitive Performance*

One of the important goals of this study is the multiple regression analysis determining which indicators of emotional-social intelligence and positive learning environment best predicts students' cognitive performance. The study states that emotional-social intelligence and a positive learning environment significantly influence the students' cognitive performance. The studies of Lee and Shute (2016) posited that there was a correlation between emotional-social intelligence and the performance of senior high school students. In addition, Alves et al. (2017) asserted that emotional-social intelligence could be used to predict students' academic success. Students' emotional and social intelligence is strongly related to a positive classroom learning environment (Galler, 2015).

Moreover, this study supports the proposition of Birknerova (2019), who mentioned that emotional and social intelligence and a positive learning environment predicts students' cognitive performance. The classroom environment is to stimulate the students' cognitive performance successfully. Emotionally and socially intelligent students can better influence and increase cohesiveness in the classroom. Teachers can also create and develop cooperative, constructive, and mutually satisfying relationships involving well-developed emotionally and socially intelligent students.

Further, the study is supported by Verma (2019) stated that a positive classroom environment affects student cognitive performance. It is mentioned that ideal learning is a classroom as positive and supportive. It is a place where students feel safe and secure. Thus, a positive and nurturing environment enhances students' cognitive ability to learn and be productive in learning independently.

According to Wilson-Fleming and Wilson-Younger (2019), teachers are allowed to improve classroom management and discipline by fostering a positive learning environment. Additionally, it gives the students a chance to think and act positively. Positive learning environments help to enhance, promote, and encourage students' cognitive performance in all academic contexts.

However, results show no correlation between emotional-social intelligence and the students' cognitive performance. This result is supported by Gutierrez-Cobo, Cabello, and Fernandez-Berrocal (2018), who mentioned that students' cognitive performance does not seem to be correlated with emotional intelligence. It is a relatively young concept that aims to link emotion and cognition, although emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, use, understand, and regulate emotions. However, it still has no relation to the student's cognitive ability.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

Conclusions are made in this section, considering the results of the study. The respondents showed a high level of emotional-social intelligence and students' cognitive performance and demonstrated a high level in a positive learning environment. The study generally revealed a significant relationship between the positive learning environment function on the cognitive performance of the students. However, the result revealed no significant relationship between emotional-social intelligence on the cognitive performance of the students. In addition, overall, the study revealed that only a positive learning environment influences the students' cognitive performance. With the results, this study supports the proposition of Birknerov (2019), who mentioned that a positive learning environment predicts students' cognitive performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the initial findings and conclusions, several recommendations are offered. The overall level of emotional-social intelligence with very high levels of responsible decision-making, self-awareness, relationship management, and social awareness commitment means that these indicators are manifested by students most of the time. In this context, students must uphold the level of emotional-social intelligence on how to keep these types of commitment in multiple directions, particularly in their studies. Acquiring the knowledge and skills required to function effectively would be possible through the help of their teachers and parents in their education subjects in connection with different instructional goals and learning conditions. Thus, this recommends that teachers and school administrators implement various activities to improve students' performance.

Also, the high level of positive learning environment derived from high levels of caring, fairness, respect, interactions with students, classroom management, and discipline of students denote that these are manifested by teachers most of the time. Education program heads are therefore advised to evaluate their programs and act in orientation, forum, and seminar to enhance a positive learning environment towards teaching and learning. They must consider these in the planning and provision of teacher training and actual classroom teaching experiences. The teachers must be afforded thorough training on changing concepts about teaching and learning to create a positive learning environment. Also, teachers must be provided with reading and other materials based on the changing concepts of teaching pedagogy vis-à-vis traditional philosophies of education. They must be asked to discuss and share this in class. In addition, teachers should demonstrate a positive learning environment at the school level based on the current teaching concepts. Thus, the students must be allowed to learn, grow, and increase their learning performances and academic achievements.

The significant relationship of positive learning environment signifies that students grow more in an environment where their receptivity to diversity, equal representation, and retain diverse students and promotion of gender sensitivity. The students must be guided by the concepts of learning diversity as it brings interaction between students with different ideas and enables achievement at the school. It is pertinent to state that learning diversity can improve students in school.

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APPENDIX A RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE

Name (Optional): _____ Grade & Section: _____
Date: _____

Direction: Please answer the following items by putting a check (/) on the column that corresponds to your answer using the following scale.

Rating	Descriptive	Interpretation
5	Always	This means that the item embodied in the statement is observed at all times.
4	Often	This means that the item embodied in the statement is observed most of the time.
3	Sometimes	This means that the item embodied in the statement is observed.
2	Seldom	This means that the item embodied in the statement is rarely observed.
1	Never	This means that the item embodied in the statement is not observed.

Part I: Questionnaire on Emotional and Social Intelligence

	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
Self-awareness <i>In our class ...</i>					
1. I know what I am thinking and doing.					
2. I understand what I do and why I do it.					
3. I understand my moods and feelings.					
4. I know when I am moody.					
5. I can read people’s facial expressions when they are angry.					
Social Awareness <i>In our class ...</i>					
1. I recognize how people feel by looking at their facial expressions.					
2. I understand why people feel the way they do easily.					
3. I believe I know what they are thinking if someone is sad, angry or happy.					
4. I understand why people react the way they do.					
5. I have a pretty good idea why a friend is upset.					
Self- management <i>In our class ...</i>					
1. I can stay calm in stressful situations.					
2. I stay calm and overcome anxiety in new changing situations.					
3. I stay calm when things go wrong.					
4. I can control my emotions when something bad happens.					
5. I will wait till I have calmed down before discussing the issue, when I am upset with someone.					
Relationship Management <i>In our class ...</i>					
1. I will always ask apology when I hurt my friend unintentionally.					
2. I always try and comfort my friends when they are sad.					
3. I try not to criticize my friend when we quarrel.					
4. I am tolerant of my friend’s mistakes.					
5. I stand up for myself without putting others down.					
Responsible Decision Making <i>In our class ...</i>					
1. I consider the consequences of my actions, when making decisions.					

2. I ensure that there are more positive outcomes in making my choice.					
3. I weigh the strengths of the situation before deciding on my action.					
4. I consider the criteria chosen before making a recommendation.					
5. I consider the strengths and weaknesses of the strategy before deciding.					

Part II. Questionnaire on Positive Learning Environment

	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
Caring					
<i>In our school our teacher/s...</i>					
1. show concerns for students’ emotional and physical well-being.					
2. create a warm and supportive classroom climate.					
3. respond to misbehavior on an individual level and privately.					
4. prevent situations in which student loses peer respect.					
Fairness and Respect					
<i>In our school our teacher/s...</i>					
1. treat students fairly.					
2. create situations for all students to succeed.					
3. show respect to all students.					
4. maintain professional role while being friendly.					
5. give students responsibility.					
Interactions with Students					
<i>In our school our teacher/s...</i>					
1. value what students say.					
2. encourage student cohesiveness and cooperation.					
3. emphasize functional communication between teacher and students and among fellow students.					
4. use consistent and proactive discipline.					
5. establish rules, routines, and procedures early in the school year.					
6. arrange smooth transitions and continuity of classroom momentum.					
7. is aware of all activities in the classroom.					
8. anticipate potential problems.					
Classroom Management					
<i>In our school our teacher/s...</i>					
use space, proximity, or movement around the classroom for nearness to trouble spots and to encourage attention.					
2. prepare materials in advance and have them ready to use.					
3. organize classroom space efficiently to support learning activities.					
4. manage the physical factors to optimize student learning.					
use effective questioning, smooth transitions and challenging but interesting activities to increase student engagement and minimize disruption.					
6. interpret respond to inappropriate behavior promptly.					
Discipline of Students					
<i>In our school our teacher/s...</i>					
1. implement rules of behavior fairly and consistently.					
2. reinforce and reiterate expectations for positive behavior.					
use both punishment and positive reinforcement to encourage desirable student behavior.					

Direction: Please answer the following items by putting a check (/) on the column that corresponds to your answer using the following scale.

Rating	Descriptive	Interpretation
5	Strongly Agree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is completely decided.
4	Agree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is decided.
3	Uncertain	This means that the item embodied in the statement is either decided or undecided.
2	Disagree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is undecided.
1	Strongly Disagree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is completely undecided.

Part III. Questionnaire on Cognitive Performance

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Memory <i>In our class I/ I am ...</i>					
1. remember concepts through written practice.					
2. good at memorization.					
3. can easily memorize the concepts with lot of illustrations.					
4. good at remembering information.					
5. like to understand all subjects instead of memorizing.					
6. have difficulty in writing without spelling mistake.					
7. able to memorize the theories and laws easily.					
8. used to go through many materials for better understanding.					
9. very good at remembering the things I have committed to do.					
10. used to memorize all my lessons as it is in the book.					
11. used to get confused, when writing the years in the subject					
Attention <i>In our class I/ I am ...</i>					
1. consciously focus my attention on information.					
2. focus on the meaning and significance of new information.					
3. able to focus on important task throughout the day.					
4. can study with full concentration for a long time.					
5. couldn't concentrate on the subject at the time of group study.					
6. used to have daydream in the class.					
7. couldn't substitute a correct formula in a right place due to lack of attention.					
Flexibility <i>In our class I/ I am ...</i>					
1. used different learning strategies depending on the situation.					
2. don't like to follow the same route while performing a task.					
3. will take other's suggestion in order to solve problems.					
4. ready to make changes.					
5. consider myself to be flexible and adaptive to change.					
6. can't easily adapt to the new environment.					
Self-Perception <i>In our class I/ I am ...</i>					
1. quick to see and take advantage of new opportunities.					
2. have no fear in challenging the views of others.					
3. work to get things done as efficiently as possible.					
4. thrive on working under pressure.					
5. will always be true to myself, no matter what the situation.					
Thinking <i>In our class I/ I am ...</i>					
1. think I can guess the correct answer.					
2. enjoy very much in deep thinking about learning strategies.					
3. never think about the step to follow in solving problems.					

4. think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one.					
5. proud that I can think correct answer.					
6. usually think of different ways to answer a question.					
7. used to memorize my lessons as it is, without thinking and analyzing about facts.					
8. used to think about the easy method to solve a problem.					

**APPENDIX B
LETTER TO CONDUCT THE STUDY**

Professional Schools
Ground Floor, Ps Building
Matina, Davao City
Telephone: (082)305-0645 Local 189

September 28, 2021

DR. DEE D. SILVA, CESO V
School Division Superintendent
Division of Davao del Norte

Dear Ma'am:

The undersigned is currently working on her thesis, **"Emotional and Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment as determinants of Cognitive Performance"** as a requirement for the degree of **Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education**.

In this regard, the researcher would like to request your approval to conduct the study in your area of responsibility and the confidentiality of the data that you will share will be carefully safeguarded. Attached herewith is a sample of the interview guide/survey questionnaire that reflects the topics and questions to be discussed.

Looking forward for your favorable response on the said request.

Respectfully yours,

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Researcher
09306815368

Noted by:

LIEZEL V. CHAN, Ph.D.
Research Adviser

EUGENIO S. GUIHAO, JR., DM
Dean, Professional School

APPENDIX C
LETTERS TO THE EVALUATORS

September 27, 2021

DR. ELDEN D. ORBETA
Education Program Supervisor
Department of Education
Division of Panabo City

Sir:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, "**EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE**" as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 21, 2021

MYLA N. MASCARIÑAS, MAED

Faculty
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, **"EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE"** as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 21, 2021

DR. LAILANIE TINGSON
Professor
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, "**EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE**" as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 21, 2021

DR. JOCELYN B. BACASMOT
PHO Applied Linguistics
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, **"EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE"** as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 21, 2021

DR. MARY ANN E. TARUSAN
Professor
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, **"EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE"** as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

APPENDIX D VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRES

 The University of Medicine	PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS Main Branch VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE
Name of Evaluator : Degree : Position : Number of Years of Teaching : To the Evaluator : Points of Equivalent :	Eileen D. Orata PhD Doctor of Philosophy Educational Program Supervisor 14 Please check the appropriate box for your ratings 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good
ITEMS	1 2 3 4 5
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. Suitability of Items The item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adopted is appropriate for the items.	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Title of the Research Questionnaire : <u>Emotional and Social Intelligence and Critical Learning Environment as determinants of Cognitive Performance.</u>	
Name of Researcher : <u>Dr. Ma. L. Gonzales</u>	
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire : <u>Oct. 8, 2023</u>	
Remarks of the evaluator : <u>He followed some of the corrections. Good work!</u>	
 EILEEN D. ORATA, PhD Signature Above Printed Name	

<p>PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS UM The University of Mindanao</p>	[] Main [] Branch _____ VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE												
Name of Evaluator Dr. Mary Ann E. Tarusan Degree Ph.D. AL													
Position RC-Offsite Number of Years of Teaching 35 years													
To the Evaluator Please check the appropriate box for your ratings													
Points of Equivalent	<table style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:25%; text-align: center;">5-</td> <td style="width:25%; text-align: center;">Excellent</td> <td style="width:25%; text-align: center;">2-</td> <td style="width:25%; text-align: center;">Fair</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">4-</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Very Good</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1-</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Poor</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">3-</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Good</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	5-	Excellent	2-	Fair	4-	Very Good	1-	Poor	3-	Good		
5-	Excellent	2-	Fair										
4-	Very Good	1-	Poor										
3-	Good												
ITEMS	<table style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:60%;"></td> <td style="width:10%; text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="width:10%; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width:10%; text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="width:10%; text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="width:10%; text-align: center;">1</td> </tr> </table>		5	4	3	2	1						
	5	4	3	2	1								
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	/												
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	/												
3. Suitability of Items The Item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	/												
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per are a category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	/												
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	/												
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/												
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/												
Title of Approved Research: EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE													
Name of Researcher: <u>Sheila Mae S. Gerolaga</u>													
Research Adviser: <u>Dr. Lizeel Chan</u>													
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: <u>9-17-21</u>													
Remarks of the Evaluator: <u>ok for administration. Please affix name and signature at the bottom of the questionnaire.</u>													
Mary Ann E. Tarusan													
_____ Signature Above Printed Name													

<b style="font-size: 2em; color: red;">UM The University of Mindanao	<h2 style="color: blue; margin: 0;">PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS</h2> [] Main [x] Branch Digos				
VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE					
Name of Evaluator : LEILANIE L. TINGZON, EdD. Degree : <u>Doctor of Education</u> Position : _____ Number of Years of Teaching : _____ To the Evaluator : _____ Points of Equivalent : _____	Please check the appropriate box for your ratings 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good				
ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	/				
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	/				
3. Suitability of Items The item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	/				
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	/				
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	/				
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/				
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/				
Title of Approved Research: <u>"EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE"</u>					
Name of Researcher: <u>SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA</u>					
Research Adviser: <u>LEIZEL V. CHAN, Ed.D.</u>					
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: <u>July 31, 2021</u>					
Remarks of the Evaluator: <u>Follow comments</u>					
 LEILANIE L. TINGZON, EdD. Signature Above Printed Name					

F-13550-011/ Rev. #3 / Effectivity: January 25, 2018

 The University of Mindanao	<h2 style="margin: 0;">PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS</h2> [<input type="checkbox"/>] Main [<input type="checkbox"/>] Branch _____				
VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE					
<p> Name of Evaluator : <u>Myla Mae N. Mascariñas</u> Degree : <u>MAED – H.E.</u> Position : <u>Faculty Member</u> Number of Years of Teaching: _____ To the Evaluator : _____ ratings Points of Equivalent : _____ </p> <p style="text-align: right; margin-right: 50px;"> Please check the appropriate box for your 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good </p>					
ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	/				
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	/				
3. Suitability of Items The Item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	/				
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	/				
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	/				
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/				
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/				
<p style="text-align: center;"> Title of Approved Research: <u>EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE</u> </p> <p> Name of Researcher: <u>SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA</u> </p> <p> Research Adviser: <u>DR. LIEZEL CHAN</u> </p> <p> Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: _____ </p> <p> Remarks of the Evaluator: <u>Congratulations! You are good to go. Just have a very few marginal notes. Pls check</u> </p>					
 MYLA MAE N. MASCARINAS Signature Above Printed Name					
F-13550-011/ Rev. # 3/ Effectivity: January 25, 2018					

UM
The University of Mindanao

PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS

[] Main [] Branch Barobo

VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

Name of Evaluator : Dr. Jocelyn B. Bacunat
 Degree : Ph.D.
 Position : Dean
 Number of Years of Teaching : 37
 To the Evaluator : _____
 Points of Equivalent : _____

Please check the appropriate box for your ratings

5 - Excellent	2 - Fair
4 - Very Good	1 - Poor
3 - Good	

ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	/				
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.		/			
3. Suitability of Items The item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	/				
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	/				
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	/				
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/				
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/				

Title of Approved Research: Emotional & Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment as Determinants of Cognitive Performance

Name of Researcher: Michelle Mae Lovelace

Research Adviser: Dr. Jocelyn B.

Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: July 26, 2021

Remarks of the Evaluator: Please take note of negative & positive statements of your questionnaire. I suggest that you change from negative statements to negative positive to avoid misinterpretation of results.

 Signature Above Printed Name

APPENDIX E UMERC CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL

ETHICS REVIEW COMMITTEE (UMERC)

Ground Floor, Professional Schools Building
Ma-a Mabina Campus, Davao City
Telephone: (082)305-0640 local 189
umethicsreviewer@umindanao.edu.ph

FORM 2.6 Certificate of Approval

Date April 23, 2022

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the **University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee** for implementation.

UMERC Protocol No.	UMERC-2022-027	Sponsor Protocol No	N/A
Principal Investigator/s	SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA	Sponsor	N/A
Title	EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AND POSITIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE		
Protocol Version No.	2	Version Date	April 18, 2022
ICF Version No.	2	Version Date	April 18, 2022
Other documents			
Members of research team			
Study sites	Davao Region		
Type of review	<input type="checkbox"/> Expedited <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Full board	Duration of Approval: From: April 23, 2022 To: September 23, 2022	Approved Meeting Date: April 23, 2022
UMERC Chairperson	Signat	Date	
HELEN Q. OMBLERO, DSD		April 23, 2022	

ETHICS REVIEW COMMITTEE (UMERC)

Ground Floor, Professional Schools Building
Ma-a Mabina Campus, Davao City
Telephone: (082)305-0640 local 189
umethicsreviewer@umindanao.edu.ph

Received by: _____
 Name: SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
 Signature: _____

Date April 23, 2022

**APPENDIX F
PUBLIC FORUM CERTIFICATE**

APPENDIX G
EDITOR'S CERTIFICATION

Professional Schools
Ground Floor, PS Building
Matina, Davao City
Telephone: (082) 297-6115

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the manuscript of **Ms. Sheila Mae S. Gerolaga**, entitled, "**Emotional and Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment as determinants of Cognitive Performance**" has been checked and edited by the undersigned in accordance with the standard mechanics, format, spacing, and references set by the university.

This certification is issued on July 07, 2023.

DAN O. GOMEZ EdD
Reader

APPENDIX H
INFORMED CONCENT FORM (ICF)

University of Mindanao
Informed Consent Form (ICF)
UNPRC - 006
Rev. 01 / December 1, 2016
Approved by:
Control No.:
University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee
Molina, Davao City
Informed Consent Form for Emotional and Social Intelligence and Positive Learning Environment as Determinants of Cognitive Performance
Name of the Researcher(s) SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Institution: University of Mindanao – Panabo City
INTRODUCTION
You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by Sheila Mae S. Gerolaga, at the University of Mindanao, because you fit the inclusion criteria for informants of our study.
Your participation is completely voluntary. Please read the information below, and ask questions about anything you do not understand, before deciding whether to participate. Please take as much time as you need to read the consent form. You may also decide to discuss participation with your family or friends.
If you decide to participate, you will be asked to sign this form. You will be given a copy of this form.
PURPOSE OF THE STUDY
This study aims to predict the emotional and social intelligence and positive learning environment as determinants of cognitive performance of Senior High School students in one of the secondary school of Carman division of Davao del Norte.
STUDY PROCEDURES
If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to participate by answering the survey questionnaire which you can finish in less than 30 minutes.
POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS
You may feel discomfort during the course of the interview because of the sensitive nature of the topic being studied. You may opt not to answer questions which make you feel any psychological or emotional distress or you can withdraw as a participant of the study if you feel that you cannot discuss the information that is asked of you. The researchers value your participation and will place your welfare as their highest priority during the course of the study. The researcher will ensure that the level of risks and measures in mitigating those possible risks will be reviewed properly. You will be protected from physical, psychological, or social economic harms during the conduct of the study to avoid risks.
POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO PARTICIPANTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY
This study can generate relevant information which can be useful to public and private administrators, human resource managers, and policy-makers. The results, discussions, and findings from this study can spark evidence-based information which can be used by government agencies such as Department of Education, school administrators, teachers, students, parents, and future researcher.
CONFIDENTIALITY
We will keep your records for this study confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information obtained in connection with this study will remain confidential, except if necessary to protect your rights or welfare. This certificate means that the researcher can resist the release of information about your participation to people who are not connected with the study. When the results of the research are published or discussed in conferences, no identifiable information will be used.

University of Mindanao
Informed Consent Form (ICF)
UNPRC - 006
Rev. 01 / December 1, 2016
Approved by:
Control No.:
PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL
Your participation is voluntary. Your refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study.
INVESTIGATOR'S CONTACT INFORMATION
If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact the researcher at the University of Mindanao, Davao City through telephone number or mobile phone number 09156810266 or through email at sheilamae@unprc.unm.edu.ph; or if you need to see her, she can be located at the Office of Tubod National High School, Carman, Davao del Norte.
RIGHTS OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT
If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about your right as a research participant or the research in general and are unable to contact the research team, or if you want to talk to someone independent of the research team, please contact the University of Mindanao Professional Schools at 305-06-43
RESEARCH PARTICIPANT'S CONSENT
I have read the information provided above. I have been given a chance to ask questions. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. I can withdraw my consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty.
Signature above Printed Name of Participant
Date Signed
To be accomplished by the Researcher Obtaining Consent:
I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.
SHEILA MAE S. GEROLAGA
Name of Person Obtaining Consent
2-15-2022
Date Signed